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**METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING CREATIVE ABILITIES OF
PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS BASED ON INNOVATION
APPROACH (IN THE EXAMPLE OF TECHNOLOGY)**

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***Abstract** – This article talks about the importance of using methods that encourage students to think creatively in technology classes, the importance of teamwork to develop their abilities, and the need for an innovative approach to each lesson.*

***Keywords:** education, innovation, creativity, ability, team, project, problem situation,*

INTRODUCTION

The founder of the PISA study, Andreas Schleicher, special adviser on education policy to the Secretary General of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), said the following in an interview with the State Inspectorate for Quality Control of Education, "Gazeta.uz":

– Education is the future of society. The economy of your country is connected with the future. Schools are your economy today, your society tomorrow. Education policy is always closely related to economic policy. No country can achieve economic success without developing a skilled human resources base and creating better conditions for highly qualified personnel in the labor market. That's why I think these two concepts are very close.[1]

It's comments on his thoughts, he had passed on again expressed thoughts like:., creativity is- to be obsessed with creative work, to be busy with creativity, to think, to discover” In general, the

concept of "Creation" does not have a single definition. This is because people do not have a single stop on what can be said to be unusual, good or useful, which is why creativity is a relative concept. Of course, the interpretation of this term also depends on the personal views of people.

Therefore, when we define this term, it can be said that it is the subject of a discussion that does not give a handle, which, figuratively speaking, slips out. In order for a voluntary process of activity to be recognized as the result of yohud or creative of some kind of idea, it must be recognized as unusual, good and useful. It is also necessary to note that as times go by, important changes are taking place in the concept of creativity and creative approach, creativity in general.

Today, creativity involves a person's ability to see the world with a new eye, demonstrate their abilities and find specific solutions to problems. In technology classes, improving student creativity as well as encouraging creative thinking, developing these qualities, provide students with great opportunities. In fact, the very nature of the organization of technology classes teaches students not only technical knowledge, but also a creative approach, since in technology classes, students create various items with their own manual labor, work on new products and implement their creative thoughts.

For example, through woodworking, needlework, or some practical art, students can freely express their ideas, or new approaches and abilities. Let's take making a flower by simply folding it out of paper as an example. In this, the teacher is able to make any flower texnologiya.

Students can achieve interesting results in combination with testing their imagination in practice. Organization of such teamwork in technology classes allows students to realize their creative ideas in unity, exchange ideas with each other, learn a new approach, at the same time form communication skills, problem-solving skills, and also teach mutual trust. It is very important to create a creative environment in technology classes. Because in such an environment, students show a sense of responsibility and the ability to think independently, and also teach them to accept mistakes and learn from them. After all, as Leo Tolstoy said „every mistake is a door for new knowledge and a new achievement.” Activists, such as project-based teaching, creating a problem situation, working with the team, increase the creative potential of students, they have confidence in the future, their own personality and strength

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